

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Time-Aware In-Cabin Driver Monitoring Ontology With Hybrid Logical Reasoning

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ABSTRACT Modern autonomous and intelligent vehicles increasingly require reliable in-cabin monitoring systems capable of interpreting complex physiological and behavioral signals to safeguard driver well-being. This paper proposes a time-aware, ontology-driven framework that unifies multimodal physiological, behavioral, and cognitive indicators into a single semantic model capable of transparent, rule-based driver-state inference. The proposed system combines GCIs for interpretable physiological threshold classification with SWRL rules for contextual and numeric reasoning, enabling transparent inference of fatigue, attention level, and unresponsiveness across sequential time windows. A 4D Description Logic architecture structures each measurement as a temporally indexed state, supporting longitudinal analysis over time-series data. To ensure robustness and scalability, real-world physiological data are augmented with synthetic physiological time series generated via TimeGAN, while the inferred driver states condition a diffusion-based image generation module for visual interpretation. The framework is evaluated through a comprehensive validation stack, including competency questions, structural consistency checks, performance profiling, image quality assessment using a self-supervised ARNIQA model and cross-model consistency using visual extractors with an LLM, demonstrating high logical consistency, accurate state inference, and stable performance across multiple distinct actors with 16 temporal slices. Results confirm that the proposed ontology-based framework provides a transparent, extensible, and computationally tractable foundation for in-cabin driver state assessment, enabling future integration with advanced Human-Machine Interface (HMI) systems and real-time intelligent vehicle applications.

INDEX TERMS Diffusion model, health, ontology, reasoning, validation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of autonomous and connected vehicles is revolutionizing the automotive industry, transforming vehicles from simple means of transportation into sophisticated, intelligent systems that prioritize safety, comfort and user well-being. With the advancement of these systems, the integration of biological and human-centric considerations

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becomes essential, necessitating capabilities such as sensing, reasoning, decision-making, learning and collaboration [1].

Given the significant amount of time individuals spend within vehicle cabins [2], the health and safety of occupants have become a growing concern. Research indicates that in-cabin air quality, often impacted by high levels of pollutants, poses significant risks to occupants' health [3]. Consequently, monitoring systems are increasingly shifting focus from environmental factors to the physiological and psychological states of occupants, enabled by the integration

of advanced sensors within vehicles. These sensors include heart rate monitors, cameras for facial analysis and motion detectors, alongside devices measuring fatigue, dizziness and other health parameters. Integrating these systems with air quality detectors provides a comprehensive view of passenger health, thereby enhancing both safety and the overall driving experience.

Modern vehicles collect rich multimodal sensor information including Heart Rate (HR), heart rate variability (HRV), respiration rate (RR), blood oxygen saturation (SpO_2) and ocular or facial indicators. However, transforming these heterogeneous measurements into comprehensible driver states remains a major challenge. Existing approaches often rely on machine learning models that however lack the ability to comprehend the real world in a manner similar to humans [4]. To capture semantic relationships and showcase a high-level understanding of symbolic approaches, commonly referred as Good Old-Fashioned AI (GOFAI) [5], that encompass constraint-based reasoning systems among others, the focus has shifted on ontologies which can use deductive reasoning engines and axioms. These are used to describe the concepts inside the Terminology Box (TBox), in order to assert new knowledge on the Assertional Box (ABox) [6]. Ontologies provide a structured and formal framework for knowledge-based representation and reasoning. For in-cabin health monitoring, they enable modeling and integration of heterogeneous data sources, fostering relationships that focus on the driver's health state, sensor information and external systems or models. Through the Web Ontology Language (OWL) [7], such connections are formalized as a mean to infer potential health risks, during a continuous time period, under predetermined physiological boundaries. Additionally, high-frequency physiological information requires structured temporal reasoning, that is not adequately tackled by conventional feature-driven methodologies.

This work introduces a novel In-Cabin Monitoring Ontology designed to formalize physiological, behavioral, and cognitive indicators within a unified semantic framework. The ontology uses General Concept Inclusions (GCIs) to classify physiological measurements into clinically informed threshold categories, augmented by Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL) rules for numeric evaluation, contextual reasoning, and personalized grouping, that extend reasoning capabilities for contextual interpretation, special cases, and exception handling. These reasoning components operate atop a four-dimensional (4D) time-slice architecture, enabling sequential inference across time-series data while leveraging batching strategies to maintain tractable performance over temporal windows. To rigorously assess the ontology's structural relationships and inferential robustness, we constructed a synthetic dataset, grounded in real-world medical knowledge, serving as a controlled testbed for evaluating both entity decomposition and reasoning behavior.

While generative approaches often leverage Bayesian Networks [8] or Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [9], the temporal dependencies, inherent in physiological signals,

render TimeGAN [10] an appropriate choice for synthesizing realistic driver-centered time-series data. The resulting pipeline ingests raw sensor measurements, augments them via TimeGAN to mitigate data sparsity, and populates the ontology with temporally segmented *ActorStates*, from which a reasoning engine infers high-level driver conditions and assigns corresponding semantic labels. These are parsed into a state-of-the-art diffusion model to transform these inferred states into visual representations. Lastly, the generated driver depictions are evaluated in terms of both image quality and accuracy of the contextual information they convey. This multi-layer validation stack includes the ARNIQA framework to assess visual obstructions, alongside two visual attribute extractors. The outcomes of these components are, then, semantically evaluated using a local large language model, resulting in a transparent, explainable and semantically grounded in-cabin driver state assessment. This validation stack is capable of demonstrating the integration potential between ontology-driven reasoning and generative models.

The main contribution of this work is the design and validation of a framework that bridges symbolic reasoning and perception for in-cabin driver state assessment. This is achieved through the following components:

- A semantically grounded in-cabin ontology, which models physiological, behavioral and cognitive states, producing high-level symbolic representations in the form of labels and enabling structured interpretation of multimodal sensor data.
- A multi-layer reasoning architecture combining GCIs with rule-based reasoning, SWRL, allowing both efficient threshold-based classification and expressive contextual inference, supporting interpretable and explainable driver state estimation.
- A temporal reasoning formulation based on 4D-DL, where discrete *ActorState* instances represent sequential snapshots of the driver's condition, thus enabling consistent reasoning over time-series physiological data.
- A cross-modal validation framework, that explicitly evaluates the alignment between symbolic outputs and visual depictions, leveraging visual attribute extractors and LLM-based semantic comparison, to quantify consistency across modalities.
- An integrated pipeline for ontology-driven multimodal representation, combining synthetic time-series generation, symbolic reasoning and diffusion-based visual synthesis, demonstrating how inferred semantic states can be propagated into a perceptual domain for interpretability and system-level validation.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews state-of-the-art ontology-based implementations, synthetic data generation methods, and health monitoring technologies. Section III delves into the pipeline's distinct components and offers insights on the holistic integration, briefly mentioning the integral

ontology components. Section IV describes in detail the concepts, modulation, 4D architecture and reasoning constraints that are incorporated into the ontology. Section V presents the evaluation through competence, consistency, accuracy, adaptability, computational performance, image quality assessment and contextual depiction accuracy. We then conclude with Section VI, which summarizes our key findings, future next steps and aspirations, and an optimization discussion focusing on scalability.

II. RELATED WORK

The rapid and extensive advancement and deployment of IoT devices, such as wearable sensors, necessitates semantic representation for heterogeneous data sources. Tailored for health-domain systems, early ontology-based health assessment and monitoring models, quickly became a staple for knowledge assertion. In this section we present the works found in literature, applicable for driver state monitoring, temporal logical reasoning, physiological measurements interpretation and data synthesis.

A. DRIVER STATE MONITORING ONTOLOGIES

Recent advancements and efforts extend the ontology's capabilities into automotive and driver behavior monitoring [11]. Commonly, ontologies have found significant applications, when interfacing the autonomous vehicle for the driver's decision-making. Da Costa et al. [12] leveraged their scenario ontology to systematically generate targeted testing scenarios for Automated Driving Systems (ADS). They, utilizing SWRL rules, formalized a logical structure similar to Horn clauses, in order to define conditions, that lead to required safety conditions. Interestingly, Armand et al. [13], defined a core ontology, focusing on one-dimensional road scenarios, using SWRL and a reasoner, such as Pellet, to perform human-like reasoning about complex road contexts, including predicting the expected behavior and chain reactions among perceived entities. In [14], the Ontology for Context Modeling (OCM) acts as a standard, shareable world model designed for driving context representation and integrating information from various data sources. The central focus, concerning vehicle interfacing and driver behavior, is the use of logical rules and reasoning mechanisms via JESS or CLIPS, to identify and compensate for sensor failures in real-time and to recognize dynamic driving events.

B. PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNAL INTERPRETATION MODELS

Zeshan et al. [15] proposed a lightweight patient ontology integrating SWRL rules, in order to support decisions tailored for health frameworks, that are based on IoT monitoring. Similarly, Elhadj et al. [16] introduced the Do-Care system. This system models wearable and environmental sensors through a dynamic and modular ontology comprised of FOAF5, SSN6/SOSA7 and ICNP8 ontologies with a scalable set of inference rules, to classify the patient's health situation into Normal/Abnormal/Wrong. Such systems provide adaptive health recommendations, supporting personalization and

data management. Lambert et al. [17] developed an ontology focused on detecting the driver's fatigue, via semantic links, which connect vehicular characteristics, facial features and physiological signals. Hamza et al. [18] leveraged embedded HR and HRV sensors for driver health monitoring. They incorporated such sensors, into a smart steering wheel and used a remote monitoring center to detect abnormalities. For logical reasoning, they rely solely on numerical thresholds, instead of formal reasoning. Lastly, Abdelhamid et al. [19], combined ontological data mining techniques with machine learning in order to reveal underlying patterns in cardiovascular disease risk factors.

C. TEMPORAL REASONING IN ONTOLOGIES

Temporal reasoning and SWRL-based inference have, slowly, been applied to other domains, such as in the work of Donkers et al. [20] that demonstrated how SWRL and SHACL rules can evaluate time-series sensor data in the context of digital twins of smart buildings, providing a staple example of rule logical reasoning on streaming data. Similarly, Zafeiropoulos et al. [21] utilized ontologies and graph-based reasoning for continuous health monitoring for Parkinson's patients. Thus, they created temporal knowledge graphs to capture wearable data and personal health records. Such architectures illustrate, the capabilities of semantic reasoning which can extend to dynamic and real-time systems, an approach that aligns with the temporal, actor-centered modeling in our proposed ontology. The systemic review in [22] showcases how ontologies represent time-sensitive domains and temporal constraints. They identify two major approaches: *reification*, often implemented via 4D-fluents (where a temporal relationship is defined as a class) and *n-quads*, that appends a time dimension to the traditional RDF triple structure. Lastly, the authors in [23] used temporal reasoning to enhance building analytics. They developed a Time Ontology, a domain-independent ontology that defines foundational temporal concepts with the ontology encapsulating the semantic definition of temporal entities along with temporal properties, storing the topological (ordering) relationships.

D. SYNTHETIC DATA GENERATION

To the best of our knowledge, in literature, there is minimal reference that outlines the synergy of an ontology with a diffusion model. In general, there are extensively detailed innovative frameworks that combine different types of knowledge-grounded mechanisms with advanced generative models. The synergy is universally achieved, by using structured or retrieved knowledge, to condition the generative process. In [24], a two-step pipeline for Multimodal Generation of radiology reports using a knowledge-grounded mechanism to enforce clinical accuracy, is presented. This includes a clinical informed schema which is used to categorize entities and relations, thereby standardizing and simplifying the factual knowledge from the visual data.

In [25], an innovative multimodal architecture designed for dialogue generation, called Zero-Resource Image-Grounded Framework (ZRIGF), is demonstrated. The synergy is realized when the generative model utilizes the prealigned multimodal representations to create insightful responses. This allows ZRIGF to create responses, that are highly contextually pertinent and image-grounded. Lastly, in [26] the Knowledge Incorporation Network (KINET) is introduced, which uses a negative enhanced knowledge approximator and a Curriculum Knowledge Decoder (BART backbone) to generate the response from the representation of knowledge facts, related to ground-truth.

E. SUMMARY

The reviewed literature shows the significant progress in ontology-assisted driver monitoring systems. Physiological signal interpretation, temporal knowledge representation and the integration of knowledge-grounded mechanisms with powerful generative models are the predominant domain use cases. Existing driver monitoring ontologies primarily focus on behavioral cues or environmental context. These rarely support detailed physiological modeling or multi-layer reasoning. Similarly, health-oriented ontologies lack temporal progression that asserts evolving driver states, even though they offer rich semantic structures. The advancements in temporal ontologies reveal the potential of rule-based and graph-based reasoning when handling time-series information. Nonetheless, they are scarcely applied to multimodal driver monitoring scenarios. Finally, although generative frameworks that leverage knowledge-grounded mechanisms have found recent deployment in healthcare and multimodal dialogue systems, there is no prior work which has experimented with the coupling of a driver monitoring ontology, with a generative diffusion model for visual interpretation. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first unified, temporally aware ontology capable of reasoning over physiological measurements and supporting downstream generative processes, thus, motivating the advancement and development of the proposed in-cabin driver monitoring ontology and its associated pipeline.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

An overview of the pipeline's processes is demonstrated in the flow diagram Figure 1. In this section, we describe the pipeline and its individual modules, outlining the synergy between our components.

A. DATA INGESTION

The incoming dataset consists of time-indexed physiological measurements describing the driver's health state at each recorded moment, complemented by demographic attributes and a timestamp per entry. As the sensing infrastructures may differ across deployments, the ontology is intentionally designed to remain agnostic to the underlying sensing modality. This enables ingestion of any structured and time-ordered physiological or demographic signals, with

minimal preprocessing employing a Python interface which preserves the semantic structure required for reasoning. Numerous studies have established correlations between physiological signals and driver drowsiness—most notably EEG-based indicators [27]—while fatigue is predominantly linked to HR, HRV, RR, and SpO_2 , with elevated HR via reduced RR intervals, irregular respiration patterns, and reductions in SpO_2 serving as strong physiological markers [28].

Directly asserting the entire dataset into the ontology and reasoning over all measurements simultaneously is computationally prohibitive, as large-scale GCIs and SWRLs evaluation induce substantial logical expansion and memory load. To address this, the ingestion pipeline employs batching, where a configurable temporal window of consecutive rows is parsed and reasoned upon independently. Each batch is transformed into a set of sequential ActorState slices, enabling temporal interpretation and trend analysis while ensuring tractable reasoning performance. This batching strategy allows the ontology to model multi-step physiological evolution consistently and efficiently, ultimately supporting accurate semantic classification of driver states over time. Note, that due to project-level constraints, there wasn't available access to a large scale real-world dataset. The available data are formed based on a limited pilot recording from a single driver, over a short driving period. Consequently, TimeGAN-based augmentation was employed to systematically stress-test the ontology across a wide range of physiologically plausible conditions, instead of emulating population-level variability. Thus, the dataset should be interpreted not as a representative real-world benchmark, but as a controlled evaluation groundwork.

This initial source of information was preferred even though the amount of information was more scarce than synthetic datasets, because in real driving scenarios collecting such data is addressed with ethical and safety concerns. However, to reveal the underlying relations between the information and the driver's physiological state, we considered employing generative artificial intelligence models to synthesize a more detailed, with higher time resolution, monitoring dataset, to have a multitude of information when experimenting with the ontology modeling. As mentioned in [29], based upon [30], it is necessary to address data quality concerns for effective knowledge management and to verify both the data as well as the ontology in terms of competence, correctness and consistency. Luckily, most of these have since been standardized as evaluation metrics, and frameworks provide easy access to them by default.

B. SYNTHETIC EXPANSION: TimeGAN

Prior to integrating the synthesis/extension of our ingested dataset, we conducted a thorough validation process to ensure logical consistency and physiological plausibility. This included a verification for the demographic and facial attributes to prevent contradictory combinations and

FIGURE 1. Ontology parsing pipeline: From data capturing to descriptive label generation.

a validation that physiological values remained within medically acceptable thresholds. The statistical properties, extracted from this dataset, were compared to the original structured sample. A similarity evaluation was conducted by applying the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) [31] test to measure statistical differences. We leveraged the TimeGAN model to capture the temporal dependencies, while preserving the statistical profile of the original dataset. The synthetic dataset does not add any new attributes. The resulting, merged, dataset provided a more comprehensive set of physiological, behavioral, and contextual features, facilitating ontology-based reasoning over diverse health conditions. A subset of 200 representative test cases was selected to ensure a diverse range of fatigued/attentive/unresponsive driver states.

C. ONTOLOGY POPULATION

The ontology is intentionally developed to manage time-series ingestion through an explicit alignment between the ontology's conceptual entities and the dataset rows. Each row is mapped to an *Observation* instance, that operates as a semantic representation. This core module is considered as a measuring event, conceptually similar to the recording process modeled in Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology. This *Observation* encapsulates all raw physiological and demographic values using dedicated data properties such as *hasHR*, *hasHRV*, *hasRR*, *hasSpO₂*, *hasDrowsiness*, *hasAge*, *hasSex*, *hasAccessories* and *hasDemographic*. *Observations* are linked to the *MonitoringManagement* entity, to represent the abstract source of data ingestion. They are also connected to the data analysis unit (DAU), which mediates the flow of measurements into the ontology. The *Observation* individual is further associated with a *MonitoringSensor*, reinforcing provenance and measurement context, without committing to any specific hardware infrastructure.

After ingestion, the ontology is populated with semantically structured individuals that represent each measurement

instance. Each time-indexed row in the input batch is first mapped to the *Observation*, recording all raw physiological values and driver's characteristics through the aforementioned data properties. Then, each *Observation* is translated into the *ActorState* instance. This is the ontological time slice, capturing the driver's condition at that moment. Following the 4D Description Logic (DL) approach, which is presented in the next section, the *ActorState* individuals represent sequential temporal snapshots that enable longitudinal reasoning. The physiological attributes become separate concept instances, associated to the *ActorState* through the *ActorStateHasPhysiologicalState*. Such instances are later classified into threshold-based categories using logical reasoning.

We consider our ontology model as a health estimation system, whose validity consequently, resides with the validity of information available, during experimentation and evaluation phases. As we will thoroughly explain later, our inference rule logical comparisons consider real-world health monitoring data, analyzing them in order to produce descriptive labels, assessing the driver's health status.

D. SYNTHETIC IMAGE DATA GENERATION FOR DRIVER HEALTH MONITORING

The synthetic image, data, generation process begins with a time-series simulation, where a generative model learns the temporal dependencies and variability in the physiological signals. We utilize the TimeGAN framework [10] to generate realistic time-series data based on the sample. Alongside biometric data, such as respiratory rate, heart rate and heart rate variability, the generated time series also includes states of facial landmarks, depicting facial expressions. This comprises the states of eyes and mouth to capture expressions, like yawing, or blinking. Based on this, we can generate still images, and, in turn, videos of passengers corresponding to the other biometric channels in a controlled manner:

For the generation of still images, we use a pre-trained stable diffusion model by Shenoda and Kim, which the

FIGURE 2. Still images, generated using DiffuGen [32] using prompt seen in Listing 1 (age="young", origin="European", sex="female", hair="with shoulder length hair", accessories=None) and aggregated to align with a time series of eye and mouth states seen in the plots below ("C" = "closed", "O" = "open").

```

1 Front view on a person in a car driving
2 through city, highly detailed. Passenger
3 cabin interior. Face of person is clearly
4 visible. Person {eye_state}. Person {
5 mouth_state}. Person is a {age}{origin}{
6 sex}{hair}{accessories}.

```

LISTING 1 Parametrized prompt. Curly braces are placeholder values for the corresponding feature found in Figure 2.

authors refer to as DiffuGen [32]. The cornerstone of the DiffuGen pipeline is its inpainting capability, which yields more control over the produced images. Thus, the inputs to the model are twofold: On the one hand, the model accepts a textual prompt, which we parametrized as seen in Listing 1. On the other hand, it accepts a base image in tandem with a polygon, which defines the part of the image inpainting should be applied to. The model's output is an image based on the input image. DiffuGen also provides a framework for the creation of labeled input data, which we did not use but instead loosely based our generation on. Our pipeline produces new, and labeled images of diverse personas in a controlled manner. It can be used to generate images on demand, as it is invoked within the larger ontology-based pipeline. Once generated the labeled images can be aggregated to form videos based on the states of facial landmarks, which we modeled as time series. Figure 2 demonstrates the aggregation of still images based on an exemplary time series of states for eyes and mouth. Every image in this series is used as a key frame and interpolated in between. For smooth, natural-looking key frame interpolation, we use the FILM model [33], from Reda et al.

The motivation for incorporating diffusion-based image generation is not to enhance operational capabilities of a driver monitoring system. With this process we are able to address the interpretability gap between symbolic reasoning outcomes and human-understandable representations. The label generation via ontology reasoning produces structured semantic representations, which even though are precise, remain abstract and challenging to intuitively interpret or validate. This image generation module serves as an auxiliary visualization layer that translates these inferred states into human-recognizable depictions. Thus, we are enabling qualitative inspection, debugging and cross-modal consistency analysis. Hence, visual generation supports system transparency and development-time validation instead of decision making in real time. The proposed framework, also, remains scalable, allowing for continuous ontology evaluation while minimizing reliance on real-world data collection. The system can effectively classify fatigue, drowsiness, attention levels, in various conditions, therefore reducing the need for high-risk real-world testing. Finally, we used compliant data generalization mechanisms to test the ontology given different scenario configurations, thus enabling the creation of synthetic health indicators, which can maintain the statistical properties and correlations observed in the real-world health monitoring data instances.

IV. IN-CABIN MONITORING ONTOLOGY

In this section, we describe our interpretation of the domain ontology which focuses on continuous measurements of a driver's physiological state. Through ontology engineering and using the General User Model Ontology (GUMO) [34] design, capable of formally representing

user-related knowledge in a machine-readable manner, we present the contextual adaptations, inference rules and independencies that flow through the in-cabin monitoring environment. Notably, the driver's physiological state can be analyzed with the logical relationships defined by the ontology model, assessing the fatigue levels and attention-responsiveness states.

A. DESIGN PRINCIPLES

The backbone of the ontology is following the Description Logic (DL) [35] theory via a bottom-up methodology, as the ontology is driven by time-series observations feeding into higher-order health states. Nonetheless, since we are defining key domain concepts and then linking them upwards to the core class and downwards to the data management system, we could also characterize our approach as middle-out. This uses specific concepts as bridges between raw inputs and driver states. Hence, we can state that our ontology was designed following a bottom-up methodology, driven by observational information, serviced through middle-out refinements. The ontology's structural hierarchy is formulated with OWL-DL axioms, ensuring decidable reasoning and consistency checks. On the contrary, threshold-based reasoning is implemented using GCI axioms and SWRL rules to involve inequalities and temporal dependencies, complementing the DL-based structure. This approach combines DL's classification power with rules' flexibility for domain-appropriate conditions.

Since our ontology was inspired by the fundamental GUMO modeling, it is a meta-ontology providing a unified schema for describing heterogeneous user models across different applications [34]. It supports user traits (e.g. age, gender, cultural background) with dynamic states (e.g. fatigue, attention, emotions) and context (situation, environment etc.). The original GUMO, also, defines concepts to be measurable values for user physiology, by modeling them as *data properties* connected to the *User* individual. Additionally, physiological states are linked to higher-level affective/cognitive constructs, which can then be contextualized from reasoning rules, demonstrating high interoperability allowing for physiological states from different sensors to be integrated, under a common representation. However, since GUMO is a top-level category, general-purpose ontology, it doesn't capture physiological models, or medical knowledge to handle temporal evaluation of health states.

Our domain ontology, focuses on capturing concrete physiological parameters, defining appropriate medical ranges and estimating longitudinal tracking for physiological factors' adaptations over time. This is a context-aware system [36], which has to infer the user's context at any given moment, resulting to system adaptation to that context. Notably, as stated in [37], such a user model often groups the users in "stereotypes", in regards to a particular characteristic, that is application-specific. Our ontology highly values the

biological differences between the male and female bodies, which consequently define the distinct numerical thresholds for each one of the physiological parameters. Age also, determines in correlation to biological sex, the normal moderate level for the driver's health state. This semantic representation of physiological parameters, environmental factors and the User's entity, facilitate the analysis of driver's fatigue, attention and responsiveness leading to eye and mouth state categorization and relative information, which are then captured in descriptive labels.

B. ONTOLOGY STRUCTURE

The structure of the ontology perceives personalized profiles, determining the physiological baselines for the driver. The ontology purposefully attaches those baselines to higher-level entities, denoting relaxation, sleepiness, attention levels and responsiveness. Importantly, the ontology is an estimation tool and not a professional health assessment model, since that would require historical-personal knowledge for the driver's health, which is almost always unavailable or blocked due to privacy legislation.

The core of our ontology implementation follows the Multidimensional Modularization Methodology (MMM) as defined in [38]. Our ontology consists of six modules:

- **Actor**: Models the driver's profile of the vehicle, capturing information in regards to outward appearance, face characteristics, accessories and demographic information as well as age and biological sex.
- **DataContainer**: Provides the Labels (the outcome of the ontology inference) and metadata for conditioning the in-cabin environment. This also includes the ActorState 4D-time slice.
- **MonitoringManagement**: Describes entities such as sensors and the main data analysis unit, whom in this case we consider as the operator for the sensors.
- **Observations**: Captures the raw information as they are derived from the sensors (or tabular dataset) at each time interval.
- **PhysiologicalState**: Consists of the raw physiological parameters (HR, HRV, RR, SpO_2), and higher order-health states such as fatigue, attention-levels, unresponsiveness and drowsiness.
- **Thresholds**: Encodes normative and personalized reference ranges that bound the physiological parameters. This is strongly correlated with the driver's profile.

These establish three dimension categories and by deducing a domain dimension that indicates what is being modeled from the ontology, the system architecture clarifies provenance of observation and processing. Lastly, a constraint structure that governs interpretation with the thresholds can later dominate the logical inference. These dimensions are orthogonal, however they interact, creating a linked but separable ontology.

The knowledge-base is described through the terminology component (TBox) and the assertion component (ABox) as the fundamental statements that must be compliant, as they

can facilitate the semantic integration problem and use reasoning capabilities for consistency evaluation [39], [40] [41]. The modules are considered as orthogonal views since they are independent, complementary and interconnected only through interfaces, such as object properties or common upper classes. For instance, all upper classes in our ontology are subclasses of `owl:Thing`.

TBox defines the conceptual schema, by including the six core classes, their hierarchical structure and domain/range constraints. The subclass hierarchies mostly denote that a characteristic belongs to the upper class, such as `Age` \sqsubseteq `Actor`. On the other hand, ABox consists of the instances/individuals, which by extend signify the data at runtime. These individuals can be drawn immediately from the raw data, such is the case for observations, or inferred via the logical rules. The relationships are equivalent to the roles -or object properties- and are captured as RBox (role box). Those roles, link the static schema with dynamic instantiations. Lastly, the PBox explains the reasoning layers, which establish the GCI/SWRL policies that go beyond OWL-DL axioms. In other words, a policy will infer the physiological attributes for fatigue/attention/unresponsiveness, based on the determined approximations for HR/HRV/RR/ SpO_2 /Drowsiness and then another policy will decide the eye/mouth state for the driver.

In practice, the ontology parses each raw time-series dataset rows as a new `ActorState` -4D temporal slice characterizing the actor- linked indirectly to the corresponding `Observation` instance and by extend, to associated physiological measurements. The policies in the PBox then operate on each actor slice concurrently, because their development focused on a more general profile per condition and ensured that the instances compared, are associated to the correct `ActorState`. The TBox centering on the `ActorState` is depicted in Figure 3.

Inside the ontology there are dominant classes, that shouldn't be transformed into properties, whereas others, don't have significant impact on the health assessment, apart from apprehending the complete user profile. From Figure 3, this is captured clearly, as characteristics such as `Demographic` are not associated with the core individual. `Demographic` affects the physiological state the least, with mixed perspectives since late 1990s [42] and more recently [43]. In a similar manner the `Accessories` class is defined, however it is an indication of the user's surrounding environment's conditions. Extreme cold conditions bring discomfort and can greatly impact the mean RR by increasing it steadily over time, whereas for prolonged cold exposure HRV can drastically adapt [44]. Women also, appear to be more sensitive to colder environments leading to stress and anxiety, than men are as per [45], which leads to Age and biological Sex having the most significant effect on the physiological profile. They have been thoroughly examined and investigated [46], [47], [48], [49] and are some important studies with critical results. In summary, it is generally

accepted that the biological Sex has a more important effect on HR and RR interval and in contrast the Age significantly impacts the HRV of the individuals. The SpO_2 is mostly unaffected from biological Sex but does decline while getting older.

Finally, we have included two separate sub-classes of `Actor` that express the state of the eyes -`EyeState`- and mouth -`MouthState`-. There have been many studies that address eye closure detection methods to associate it with fatigue levels. Prevalent examples consider blinking frequency with a widely accepted metric known as PERCLOS defined as the percentage of eyelid closure over the pupil over time [50], [51]. Similarly, yawning duration and frequency are strongly correlated with relaxation, sleepiness and drowsiness, and are usually captured through vision deep learning models [52]. In our use case, we have no recollection of the eye or mouth state as part of the input information, so using logical reasoning, we are estimating what their status will be based on physiological measurements. This can be considered a binary classification solution, as the options are 'Open/Closed' for both states.

C. OBJECT PROPERTIES AND THRESHOLDS

The object properties assert the semantic relationships that need to be established for the ontology, in order to make assumptions and draw conclusions, particularly for the `ActorState` slices, observations and the physiological or behavioral attributes derived from the dataset. The core property, `ActorStateHasPhysiologicalState` links each actor state instance to the physiological measurements as follows:

```
ActorState  $\sqsubseteq$ 
 $\exists$ ActorStateHasPhysiologicalState.
PhysiologicalSignal
```

This central property enables treating every measurement as a distinct individual, rather than a raw numeric entry. Due to this separation, GCIs can classify physiological states according to threshold-dependent categories. Complementary, object properties such as:

```
ActorState  $\sqsubseteq$ 
 $\exists$ ActorStateHasFatigue.
FatigueLevel,
ActorState  $\sqsubseteq$ 
 $\exists$ ActorStateHasAttention.
AttentionLevel,
```

connect each `ActorState` to higher-level cognitive or behavioral classifications inferred through GCI and SWRL reasoning. Temporal alignment is maintained with:

```
ActorState  $\sqsubseteq$   $\exists$ prevState.ActorState,
```


FIGURE 3. TBox demonstration focusing on the 4D time slice: ActorState.

which services ordering of ActorState slices and supports the 4D-DL model. Additional provenance-related properties, including ObservationsAreCapturedBySensor, ObsIsDividedIntoActor and ObsIsDividedIntoPhS, capture source and measurement context without binding the ontology to any particular hardware. Collectively, these object properties form the semantic backbone of the ontology, ensuring that all temporal information is represented explicitly, modularly, and in a manner of conducive to automated reasoning. Age, sex and temperature categorization are also enabled through properties AgeBelongsToGroup, SexBelongsToGroup, AccessoriesIncludeWearables, DenotesTemperature, which are then employed by SWRL reasoning.

The threshold profiling mechanism is similarly, tightly integrated with the ontology’s object property structure. Profiling, maps physiological measurements systematically to semantic categories. Each value is instantiated as a separate individual connected to a single ActorState. Threshold profiles represent domain specific categorization schemes and are modeled as dedicated individuals associated with a set of ‘applies’ object properties (e.g. appliesHR, appliesHRV, appliesRR). Raw numeric observations are defined as the boundary conditions, which form the semantic regions including Very Low HR, Moderate RR or Critical SpO₂. As the actor state instance populates the ontology, its physiological individuals inherit their corresponding threshold profile allowing GCIs to evaluate the relevant thresholds and classify each physiological signal accordingly. Such a modular separation, ensures that threshold logic is fully externalized from the dataset and encoded within the ontology.

An overview of the threshold profiles is demonstrated in Figure 4 captured from Protégé. The threshold profiles are all designed based on the available values for sex, age and temperature, which shape the names for the individuals (e.g. tp_elderly_female_cold, tp_elderly_male_cold). The values of a threshold profile are determined via approximately 200 numerical ranges.

This design closely follows the principles of DL as it establishes thresholds explicitly defined as individuals and links them to the actors through their states, using well-formed object properties. Thus, the reasoning engine can then apply DL axioms and SWRL rules to infer the range of the measurement, classifying it consistently.

D. REASONING LAYERS

In this subsection we present the reasoning layers that support the assertions based on the TBox defined inside the ontology. These are included inside the PBox and infer relationships to the ABox.

1) GCI-FIRST REASONING LAYER

A set of named pattern classes is the core implementation for the GCI layer. These capture both single-attribute categorizations and multi-attribute signatures over combinations of HR, HRV, RR, SpO₂ and Drowsiness. Class definitions include ActorState_Very_Low_HR, ActorState_Moderate_RR and ActorState_Drowsiness_Level_3 as subclasses of ActorState with equivalent class axioms that constraint the physiological patterns via the ActorStateHasPhysiologicalState object property. The corresponding ‘is’ property (e.g. HRis, HRVis, etc.) contributes by showcasing the individual, assigned to the level of each physiological

FIGURE 4. LEFT: List of All threshold profiles | RIGHT: The object properties connecting the profile to various ranges.

measurement. Formally, a representative axiom has the structure:

```
ActorState_Moderate_HR ≡ ActorState
  ⊔ ∃ ActorStateHasPhysiologicalState.
  (HR ⊔ HRis = moderate_hr_instance)
```

The pattern is repeated for all univariate categories. This ensures, that once an ActorState has been associated with an HR individual whose HRis value classifies as moderate_hr_instance, the reasoner can consistently categorize that state into the corresponding pattern class. On top of these abstractions, we introduce a second level of GCIs as composite ActorState subclasses. Meaningful signatures across physiological dimensions grouped by drowsiness level, are encoded in a clinical manner. For instance, the class ActorState_HighHR_LowHRV_HighRR_NormalSpO2_LVL3 can be defined as:

```
ActorState_HighHR-
_LowHRV_HighRR_NormalSpO2_LVL3
≡ ActorState
  ⊔ ActorState_High_HR
  ⊔ ActorState_Low_HRV
  ⊔ ActorState_High_RR
  ⊔ ActorState_Normal_SpO2
  ⊔ ActorState_Drowsiness_LVL3,
```

and is further constrained by value restrictions such as:

```
ActorStateHasFatigue = awake_instance
ActorStateHasAttention = attentive_
instance
ActorStateHasUnresponsiveness =
responsive_instance
```

Leveraging the python interface OWLREADY2, the GCIs are implemented using the equivalent_to and is_a lists. The logical signature is defined by the former, whereas the latter materialized the appropriate fatigue/attention/unresponsiveness assignments as object property value restrictions. This aligns, with a two-stage DL design pattern where univariate GCIs, map physiological individuals to coarse categories and are combined with composite GCIs, that map conjunctions of those categories to a unique high-level interpretation of the ActorState. Notably, all reasoning remains in the OWL 2 DL fragment, with classification being monotonic and the reasoner, exclusively, required to perform structural subsumption and instance checking. Hence, no numeric built-ins or non-monotonic constructs are used in this layer. The combinatorial complexity of the multi-attribute state interpretation is, thus, compiled into a finite set of named classes, making inference predictable and scalable for batch-wise processing of multiple ActorState slices.

2) SWRL SECOND REASONING LAYER

Complementary, we define SWRL rules to assess numeric comparisons and string based grouping, with relative threshold-profile selection. Therefore, these rules replace challenging tasks which cannot be expressed purely in OWL-DL. We developed a ruler creator structure to capture the age-groups with a typical pattern:

```
ActorState(?act_st)
^ActorStageHasAge(?act_st, ?age_inst)
^hasAgeValue(?age_inst, ?age_value)
^swrl::greaterThanOrEqual(?age_value, 0)
^swrl::lessThan(?age_value, 18) →
AgeBelongsToGroup(?age_inst, young_
instance)
```

Correspondingly, SWRL built-ins operated on typed numeric literals and the rule concludes with a semantic grouping

assertion. This way, sex, accessories (etc.) are classified through string-based built-ins with inputs such as 'Man' or 'Glasses' into ontology-level groups. These grouping assertions are then reused by other rules to derive the threshold profiles as shown in Figure 5, visualized through the AOWLNL [53] capability.

Physiological thresholds are handled with this pattern hierarchy considered, comparing `Observation` values against the numeric ranges derived from clinical guidelines, then assert the appropriate `-is` value individually. Subsequently, these values are parsed using the GCI pattern classes described previously. That way, SWRL is used only where datatype reasoning or string normalization is required, with the outcome of these rules always matching an ontological assertion, feeding purely DL-based classification layer.

This separation assists in controlling complexity and improves the reasoner's inference convergence. Additionally, trend analysis operations further exemplify this decomposition of labor, as detecting persistent abnormalities can be written as trend tags back into the ontology, which are then interpreted by additional GCIs such as `StartingDrowsyFatigueTrend` that maps these tags to refined fatigue levels.

3) 4D-DL TIME SLICE INFERENCE

Each row of the time-indexed dataset sample corresponds to an `ActorState` slice captured by the 4D-DL time-slice architecture, which models the driver as a temporally extended object, with instantaneous conditions. For a batch of rows or for every timestamp `ts_iso` that is parsed, the system creates a new set of instances `HR`, `HRV`, `RR`, `SpO2`, `Drowsiness`, `Age`, `Sex` and `Accessories`, linking them to a newly instantiated `ActorState` with a `validAt` time index. Such slices, are ontologically independent but semantically ordered by the external data stream and processing logic. The reasoner, thus, is allowed to operate on top of a bounded temporal window, still supporting longitudinal analysis. The GCIs and SWRL rules previously discussed operate on every slice, providing it with a fully classified label triplet.

This architecture, combined with an external trend analysis layer that processes sequences of recent `ActorState`, results in temporal trends. Our trend analysis module maintains a sliding window of the latest label dictionaries in order to have custom detectors to determine if a clinically meaningful pattern can be recognized. When a pattern is detected the latest `ActorState` in the window is annotated with a trend tag such as `hasFatigueTrend = "fatigue_starting_drowsy"`. These tags are propagated to the DL-structure using GCIs such as:

```
StartingDrowsyFatigueTrend
≡ ActorState
⊑ hasFatigueTrend
= 'fatigue_starting_drowsy',
```

with `is_a` enforcing `ActorStateHasFatigue = drowsinesssuspected_instance`. Concluding, this architecture approach preserves the 4D-DL view, while enabling temporal reasoning over short histories, without overloading the DL reasoner with complex temporal constructs. Consequently, the system can capture both instantaneous physiological states, and evolving risk patterns in a computationally controlled manner.

E. ONTOLOGY VALIDATION STACK

We validate the ontology through a combination of logical, functional and performance-oriented checks. The aim is to showcase the semantic consistency and appropriate knowledge assertion, when data flow through the ontology architecture, leveraging a custom Competency Questionnaire (CQ), primary metrics to assess the size and complexity, correlating to the reasoner's inference performance and expressivity, which influences the reasoner's tableau construction. However, we also extend our validation approach by developing a multi-layer validation framework stage, combining symbolic ontology reasoning, visual attribute extraction and LLM-based semantic comparison to verify the contextual continuation after the image generation, in order to match the ontology generated labels with the driver depictions. It is important to address that the focus of this validation stack is to verify logical soundness, inferential correctness and robustness as a reasoning system, rather than to establish external clinical validity. In regards to the second validation stage, the key point is not measuring classification accuracy, but obtaining semantic agreement between ontology labels and visual perception outputs, hence the similarity should be interpreted as degrees of consistency. This validation stack is intentionally decomposed into independent layers, each evaluating a different component of the system rather than forming a closed-loop validation.

1) COMPETENCY QUESTIONNAIRE (CQ)

The initial validation stage relies on the Competency Questionnaire (CQ), a suite of SPARQL-based queries designed to assess the ontology's conceptual soundness, inferential completeness, and robustness across temporal driver states. Each query operates on a fully materialized ABox, after all GCIs and SWRL rules have been applied, ensuring that the evaluation reflects the ontology exactly as it will be consumed by downstream components. Consequently, CQ results capture both structural correctness and the reliability of the ontology's reasoning behavior. The first group of queries (Q1–Q14) establishes foundational modeling integrity by verifying the completeness and functional cardinality of each `ActorState`. Q1–Q6 ensure one-to-one correspondence between physiological measurements and their associated states, while Q7–Q13 confirm that each high-level semantic attribute (fatigue, attention, unresponsiveness) appears exactly once per state. Q14 extends this validation to demographic and accessory characteristics,

FIGURE 5. Left Hand side (LHS) rule declaration for threshold profiling, and Right Hand Side (RHS) assertion.

collectively forming the baseline cognitive architecture of the system.

The next series (Q15–Q20) focuses on the ontology’s physiological reasoning machinery, particularly threshold-based classification. Q15A–E verify that no physiological instance is assigned to more than one level class, ensuring mutually exclusive and exhaustive threshold partitions. Set Q16A–E confirms that each measurement receives exactly one classification; failures here signal incomplete numerical boundaries or conflicting rules. Q17A–E supplement these checks by detecting improper level propagation or overlapping constraints—issues that commonly arise in expressive OWL ontologies. Higher-order semantic dependencies are validated through Q18–Q20, which test clinical causality constraints (e.g., relationships between severe drowsiness and inattentiveness). Q21–Q26 evaluate adaptability and structural coherence, including correct threshold-profile assignment, absence of unused physiological categories, and resilience to semantic drift. Q27–Q33 further assess alignment between drowsiness levels and their behavioral implications, as well as the correct identification of dangerous edge-case combinations.

Finally, Q34–Q35 verify the correctness of Label propagation, ensuring that risk-critical states are linked to the appropriate label individuals and that no label remains without a corresponding ActorState. As label generation is achieved through object-property assertions, these final checks confirm the integrity of the pipeline’s terminal reasoning stage and its readiness for downstream diffusion-model integration. A representative CQ pattern is shown next to illustrate the structure of these validation rules.

```

1
2 # -----
3 # Q20. Violation "Sleep or
4 # -----
5 # SELECT ?state ?fat ?unresp ?eye ?
6 # WHERE {
7 #   ?state rdf:type :ActorState .
8 #   OPTIONAL { ?state :
9 #     ActorStateHasFatigue ?fat . }
10 #   OPTIONAL { ?state :
11 #     ActorStateHasUnresponsiveness ?unresp . }
12 #   # Eye state is an individual linked
13 #   # to a category via :EyeStateIs
14 #   OPTIONAL {?state :ActorHasEyeState ?
15 #     eye .
16 #     ?eye :EyeStateIs ?
17 #     eyeCat . }
18 #   OPTIONAL { ?state :
19 #     ActorHasMouthState ?mouth . }
20 #   FILTER (
21 #     ( (?fat = :Sleep) || (?unresp = :
22 #       Unresponsive) )
23 #     &&
24 #     (!BOUND(?eyeCat) || ?eyeCat != :
25 #       closedstate_instance ||
26 #       !BOUND(?mouth) || ?mouth != :
27 #         mouth_open_instance ) )
28 # }

```

2) CONSISTENCY AND METRICS

Our custom CQ complements the validation stack by emphasizing the ontology’s ability to capture information

correctly and assert individuals to the appropriate classification. However, ontologies are also evaluated based on computational performance along with consistency. Primary metrics include the number of classes, objects, axioms, properties and individuals used inside the ontology [54], [55]. These fundamental metrics assist in assessing the size and complexity of the knowledge base. In addition to these we also capture:

- DIT (Depth of Inheritance Tree): the maximum number of superclasses from the class up to the root class. (`owl:Thing`)
- NOC (Number of children class): the number of direct subclasses a class has.
- RCH (Expression Richness): the ratio of *Anonymous* class expressions such as property restrictions, unions and intersections, to *Named* classes.

These structural metrics correlate to classification performance, with RCH measuring the logical definitions' complexity, influencing the reasoner's tableau construction. Subsequently, we focus on *DL Expressivity*, which is represented through labels that correspond to OWL2-DL. Expressivity defines reasoning complexity, indicating the reasoner's inference performance. We utilize ROBOT [56], a command-line tool and library, for automating ontology development tasks. The output provides the OWL2 profile which is the most practical way to measure expressivity. This corresponds to specific DLs:

- OWL2 EL $\approx \mathcal{E}\mathcal{L}^{++}$: Polynomial time complexity
- OWL2 QL $\approx \mathcal{D}\mathcal{L}\mathcal{F}$: Logarithmic time complexity for query answering
- OWL2 RL : Rule-based complexity
- OWL2 DL $\approx \mathcal{S}\mathcal{R}\mathcal{O}\mathcal{I}\mathcal{Q}(\mathcal{D})$: High complexity

Lastly, we developed a formal consistency report that partitions the physiological measurements, presence of exactly one classification, through a configuration dictionary of entity names. Hence, the CQ can be perceived as a closed-box that tests over the final RDF graph after the reasoner's inference, whereas the remaining validation stack in regards to the ontology, is the open-box, which checks inside the OWLREADY world and framework interface. The consistency and classification validation overlaps exist in distinct layers and are not strictly redundant, as separate layers safeguard the graph as understood by any SPARQL consumes.

3) IMAGE QUALITY ASSESSMENT

To ensure the visual fidelity of the synthetic images generated by the diffusion model that employs the semantic representation provided from the ontology, we incorporated an Image Quality Assessment (IQA) module which focuses exclusively on the perceptual image quality, excluding any semantic validity of the physiological state depicted. The semantic evaluation stage is presented in the next subsection. The IQA component is built upon the ARNIQA framework, combining a SimCLR self-supervised encoder for robust feature extraction with a lightweight regression head to estimate Mean

Opinion Scores (MOS). The model was trained using the synthetic dataset with an 80/20 split, extensive augmentation to enhance generalization, and hyperparameter optimization via the Optuna framework. Both Mean Squared Error (MSE) and ranking-based optimization objectives were applied to align predictions with human-perceived quality rankings and score deviation minimization.

4) VISUAL ATTRIBUTE EXTRACTOR

At this stage a contextual evaluation was necessary to compare the information expressed by the ontology with the driver depiction from the image generation process. For each input driver image generated, we leverage the DeepFace [57] framework component, a deep convolutional neural network for facial analysis. As a model, it estimates high-level semantic attributes from the face, including age, gender, demographic (race) and dominant emotion. These attributes directly correspond one-to-one to the label characteristics from the ontology parser, apart from the emotion estimation. This design enables automatic comparison between the expected driver characteristics and what the model detects visually in the generated image. Nonetheless, an additional visual extractor is required to define the eye and mouth state of the depicted driver. This portion of the stack integrates a custom EyeMouthExtractor module based on the MediaPipe framework [58], that determines the eye and mouth states using facial landmark geometry to compute metrics such as Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) and Mouth Aspect Ratio (MAR), which quantify the relative distances between the eyelid and lip landmarks. This way the system can classify the eye and mouth states as open or closed. These visual cues are directly related to behavioral states, associated with high-level semantic attributes from the ontology reasoning process.

The outcomes of the models are incorporated into a single label that matches the format of the ontology-generated set. We consult a local Large Language Model (LLM), provided with both descriptions (ontology-label, visual attribute label) to evaluate the consistency between them. We integrate the Gemma3:12 [59] and submit both labels in a single prompt for semantic interpretation. This LLM-based evaluation complies two strategies: Attribute-Matching and Semantic Comparison. Attribute-Matching refers to performing a strict attribute-by-attribute comparison from the fields included in the labels. Contrastingly, the LLM can validate the two label sets using the overall semantic consistency between them. Thus, instead of comparing attributes through deterministic metrics that would verify exact attribute agreement, the LLM is encouraged to verify contextual similarities adhering to logical rules. The aspiration is to provide the LLM with enough context for evaluation, to reason about relationships. It is important to note, that the LLM is not used as a ground-truth oracle, but as a semantic comparator capable of identifying agreement or contradiction between structured representations.

This creates a triangulation mechanism. In the case the ontology labels, the generated image and the perception models are in agreement, the label is likely consistent with the visual content. Nonetheless, if they diverge, the system can detect semantic inconsistencies. Thus, this validation strategy uses a different abstraction level for each of these layers, introducing a context-aware validation stack using an LLM that compares structured ontology labels, as if they were descriptions of two humans. Our approach adds the semantic reasoning, topping of symbolic and visual outputs, by treating the validation as a multi-layered reasoning problem and not as classification accuracy. We stress that this final stage does not validate the correctness of the ontology nor the generative model independently, but instead evaluates whether independently derived representations remain semantically compatible. For more information on this validation stage such as prompt-engineering and evaluation, we provide a detailed explanation in Appendix.

V. EVALUATION

The evaluation is structured to separately assess (i) the correctness and robustness of ontology reasoning, and (ii) the consistency of cross-modal representations. These evaluations should not be interpreted as an end-to-end system validation, but as complementary analyses of individual system components.

In this section, we present the experimental results from deploying the ontology as the core instrument, to categorize the driver's health state and to generate precise annotations that are later passed into the image generation process. While competency questions and consistency checks cannot establish absolute domain correctness, they provide a necessary and rigorous means of validating the ontology with respect to its intended semantics and modeling assumptions. This experimentation tested the ontology with different batch sizes and distinct driver profiles. The results showcase the ontology at the initial stage, that includes the threshold profiles' individuals, the GCI and the SWRL rules, and after inference through the reasoner, with established relationships and active individuals. In this work, CQs are not used solely to demonstrate logical self-consistency, but to systematically assess numerical threshold partitioning, exclusivity and exhaustiveness of physiological classifications, correctness of GCI and SWRL-driven inferences, and stability of high-level semantic dependencies across realistic temporal trajectories. As such, the presented results validate the ontology as the core reasoning component, while the remaining modules are evaluated in terms of compatibility rather than predictive accuracy.

A. COMPETENCE QUESTIONNAIRE

The results of the competency questionnaire captured in Table 1 demonstrate that the ontology exhibits high structural integrity, complete numerical coverage, and consistent inferential behavior across all evaluated actor trajectories. Foundational checks (Q1–Q14) reported no missing physiological

attributes, no violations of functional cardinality, and no duplicated or inconsistent high-level descriptors, indicating that both the ingestion pipeline and the GCI/SWRL reasoning layers produce well-formed ActorStates. Similarly, all threshold-partitioning queries (Q15–Q20) confirmed that every HR, HRV, RR, SpO₂, and Drowsiness instance was classified into a single and correct level, with no evidence of multi-membership or unclassified individuals. These findings validate the correctness of the numerical profiling and confirm that the ontology's physiological categorization rules are stable, exclusive, and exhaustive across the full dataset.

Higher-level semantic reasoning, evaluated through Q21–Q35, also demonstrated strong consistency. All ActorStates were successfully linked to threshold profiles (Q21), and no future or unused categories were detected (Q23). Monotonic semantic dependencies, such as the expected influence of increasing drowsiness on fatigue, attention, and unresponsiveness, were satisfied for all cases (Q27–Q33). However, three focused areas requiring refinement emerged: incomplete accessory/demographic mappings (Q14), a subset of threshold profiles missing age/sex bindings (Q26), and three high-risk states lacking corresponding labels (Q34). Specifically, for Q14, there is a limitation on the included profiles for both accessories and demographic characteristics. Hence, the ontology, was incapable of understanding non-instantiated individuals. Similarly, for Q26 where all captured threshold profiles are attributed to explicit age and sex restrictions, along with the corresponding object properties. Lastly, Q34 indicates that there is a lack of edge-case reasoning statements, exposing the ontology for high-order cognitive attributes not asserted and defaulting to an Undefined classification.

These issues stem not from reasoning failures but from modeling gaps in regards to edge-case demands, and they remain localized without affecting the broader inference logic. Overall, the CQ evaluation confirms that the ontology provides a robust and logically coherent framework, with only isolated areas requiring targeted rule or data-model adjustments.

B. CONSISTENCY

We present the formal consistency report which focuses on time misalignment, orphan states, non-classified physiological attributes, multi-membership and cardinality on the inferred fatigue/attention/unresponsiveness. Such validation is appropriate, only, after the reasoner infers knowledge, hence it includes all batched actor states and their corresponding attributes.

Figure 6 presents the distribution of inference completeness across 200 actor-cases, each consisting of 16 sequential ActorState slices. For every state, the ontology was required to infer all three high-level descriptors, providing a maximum possible score of 16/16 per actor. Any state missing one of the three attributes, reduced the actor's score by one. The resulting distribution, therefore, reflects the robustness

TABLE 1. Competency question evaluation results.

CQ ID	Competency Question / Objective	Query Result	Interpretation
Q1	ActorState missing physiological attributes	✓ No violations	Association through the ActorStateHasPhysiologicalState
Q2-Q6	Multiple instances of each attribute for ActorState.	✓ No violations	Functional requirements for physiological attributes
Q7	ActorState missing high-level attributes	✓ No violations	Correct initialization of the ActorState after data loading
Q8-Q13	Multiple instances of high-level attribute for ActorState.	✓ No violations	Functional requirements for high-level attributes
Q14	Multiple Accessories/Demographic/FaceCharacteristics for ActorState	✗ Inconsistencies found (5)	Distinct object properties for each characteristic
Q15A-E	Physiological instances classified to more than 1 level class	✓ No violations	Numerical threshold profiling validation
Q16A-E	Physiological instances successful classification	✓ No violations	GCI-reasoning validation
Q17A-E	Physiological instances multiple classification	✓ No violations	Multiple classification for each physiological attribute
Q18-Q20	Edge Cases (e.g. Sleep defines ActorState as inattentive and unresponsive)	✓ No violations	Consistency on edge case (OWL-DL axioms)
Q21	Each ActorState is assigned a threshold profile	✓ No violations	Active threshold profiling
Q22	Unused threshold profiles	✗ Inconsistencies found (17)	Single-Actor threshold profile
Q23	Future Categories accidentally left unmapped	✓ No violations	Unused IRI in RHS of any axiom or rule
Q24	New Data falls outside modeled thresholds	✓ No violations	Numerical threshold boundaries
Q25	New State appearance not referenced during reasoning	✓ No violations	ActorState not assigned inference values
Q26	Future adaptability often breaks	✗ Inconsistencies found (7)	Threshold profiles missing Age/Sex
Q27-Q31	Drowsiness influence on ActorState	✓ No violations	Distinct cases for all drowsiness levels
Q32-Q33	High-risk States inference consistency	✓ No violations	Eye/Mouth and Fatigue/Attention/Unresponsiveness outcome
Q34	High-risk state and Label association	✗ No violations	Critical physiological assessments captured
Q35	ActorState linked with Label	✓ No violations	Label Generation validation

FIGURE 6. Distribution of ontology inference completeness across 200 actor-cases, each evaluated over 16 temporal ActorStates. The chart shows how many actors achieved full inference coverage (16/16) and how many experienced partial coverage due to missing fatigue, attention, or unresponsiveness classifications in one or more states.

of the GCI-driven reasoning layer when applied to realistic, temporally structured data.

While many actors achieved perfect inference coverage, a noticeable portion exhibited between 1 and 11 missing inferences. These degradations are not random; rather, they indicate specific physiological combinations, especially complex transitions for which no GCI patterns currently exist. In such cases, the reasoner lacks sufficient rule coverage

to assign all three high-level attributes. Nevertheless, the ontology demonstrates high stability overall, with misses confined to consistent edge-case clusters rather than sporadic reasoning failures. Addressing these cases would require expanding the GCI or SWRL rule base, at the cost of increased reasoning complexity.

The consistency evaluation further confirmed that the ontology maintains strict structural and temporal correctness across all actors. No physiological instance was assigned to multiple level classes, and no measurements remained unclassified, validating the exclusivity and completeness of the thresholding profiles. All identity constraints were satisfied: each (ActorState, validAt) key appeared exactly once, with no missing timestamps, missing actor links, or duplicate entries. Likewise, no orphan states, timestamp misalignment, or reused physiological measurements were detected, ensuring batch independence and clean temporal transitions within the pipeline. Furthermore, accessory and demographic data, including temperature mappings and wearable attributes, were consistently typed and properly linked, with no unsupported or missing metadata.

Lastly, the ontology falls into the OWL2 DL profile. This confirms that the ontology is of the highest computational complexity, among the OWL profiles, and reasoners such

TABLE 2. Performance results, captured before and after inference.

	Preparation	After Sync
CPU Util(%)	5.30	123.10
Memory Util(%)	16.6	20.1
Reasoning Time (sec)	10.06	92.13
Throughput (states/s)	-	0.17

as the Pellet we use, are forced to leverage tableau algorithms to classify and check consistency. This is the primary performance restriction. But the trade-off is that we have maximized expressiveness, thus, our ontology can define intricate concepts using powerful constructs and complex class equivalences, leading to precise and detailed domain modeling. Collectively, these results demonstrate that the ontology achieves full structural consistency, complete classification coverage, and temporal coherence across all evaluated scenarios, providing a reliable foundation for high-level reasoning and downstream diffusion-model conditioning.

C. PERFORMANCE AND SCALABILITY

For the core computational efficiency we present the reasoning time (inference speed), the CPU utilization and the RAM utilization percentages consumed by the reasoner, especially important for the large ABoxes, and we also offer the throughput achieved measurement as a good input metric to correlate it with the reasoning time. These results are captured in Table 2 and represent the performance on the largest batch size (16).

Preparation is the process of loading the ontology and parsing into it the GCIs and SWRLs along with generating, once, all the threshold profiles. Conversely, inference is the process of using the syncing capabilities of the reasoner to capture all the forged relationships and individuals. From Table 2, reasoning peaked at a state where it was essentially consuming an entire core and 23% of a second CPU core. This demonstrates that the reasoner, Pellet, is effectively using parallelism (multi-threading) to speed up the inference process. Memory utilization is also low around 4% between initialization and inference, even though every `ActorState` instance along with its corresponding attribute and the established relationships, are included. Additionally, we execute the reasoner's syncing, to assert inside the ontology the logical comparison statements. The inference time is on average around 90-100 seconds, directed by batch size with an average throughput of approximately 0.15-0.20 states per seconds. Notably, we experimented with higher batch sizes, however, the size of the knowledge based increased almost exponentially, creating heap memory problems and out-of-memory errors. As for the initial reasoning time, where we synchronize the reasoner once to capture the logical statements, an average 10 seconds is fast, even though it is dependent on the number of GCIs and SWRLs, accounting also for the number of class instances already defined.

The total number of logical-reasoning statements is set to 138, which is the multitude of axioms that require a separate rule engine. Respectively, the total number of GCIs used can be determined as the anonymous class expressions within the `equivalent_to` and `is_a` properties, assessing the logical definition richness that contributes to high reasoning time, regardless of the formal format of GCIs. To demonstrate the total number of GCIs we present the comprehensive Table 3, that holds information for the initial ontology, that only includes minimum class instances and classes, the ontology after SWRLs and GCIs have been included and the ontology after inference.

Table 3 compares three ontology states: the *Original ontology*, the logical model *After SWRL/GCIs (no inf.)*, and the fully materialized ontology *After Inference*. The transition from the original schema to the SWRL/GCI-enriched version marks a substantial increase in formal expressivity. The overall size of the knowledge base grows by 112%, driven primarily by an expansion in axiom count. The TBox undergoes the largest transformation, with a 261% increase in axioms, due to the introduction of complex GCIs, equivalent class definitions, and rule-induced structural constraints. Named vocabulary nearly doubles, and the TBox incorporates 405 new anonymous classes, reflecting a shift toward definition-heavy modeling. The resulting RCH value of 1.89 indicates that each named class participates, on average, in nearly two complex expressions, confirming that the ontology now relies on deeper logical structuring, rather than simple hierarchical subsumption.

Applying the reasoner, results at an even more pronounced expansion, at the ABox level. The inference step contributes 1,224 new logical axioms, all of which appear in the ABox, demonstrating that reasoning primarily asserts **new factual knowledge**. Furthermore, the reasoner generates 240 new individuals, a direct consequence of existential restrictions and rule-driven object property creation. This is confirmed by an identical +240 increase in Signature Entities, indicating that new instances are explicitly named and incorporated into the knowledge base. Importantly, core TBox metrics such as Max DIT and Max NOC remain unchanged, confirming that reasoning does not alter class definitions, but instead enriches the instance layer with substantial inferred knowledge. Overall, this transformation highlights the ontology's high semantic productivity and its ability to derive meaningful, previously implicit information from structured driver data.

In summary, the elevated RCH and the dramatic expansion of the TBox underline, that initial classification time is the most performance-critical stage. Meanwhile, the reasoner's ability to efficiently generate large numbers of ABox axioms and new individuals, demonstrates strong ABox scalability, validating the ontology's suitability for sustained continuous data streams requiring complex instance-level reasoning.

D. ARNIQA-EVALUATION

The ARNIQA-based trained model demonstrated strong agreement with ground-truth MOS, achieving a Mean

TABLE 3. Comparison of ontology metrics across development stages.

Metric	Original ontology	After SWRL/GCIs (no inf.)	After inference
Axiom count	1333	2827	4291
Logical axiom count	873	2117	3341
Class count	107	218	218
Individual count	218	289	529
Object property count	74	74	74
Data property count	28	28	28
Datatype count	6	5	5
ABox axiom count	434	725	1949
TBox axiom count	365	1318	1318
RBox axiom count	74	74	74
TBox+RBox axiom count	439	1392	1392
Signature entity count	437	618	858
Max DIT	5	5	5
AVG DIT	4.29	4.29	4.29
Max NOC	20	111	111
AVG NOC	0.97	3.07	3.07
Anonymous Classes	0.0	405	405
Named Classes	103	214	214
RCH	0.0	1.89	1.89

Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.159, Spearman correlation of 0.903, and Pearson correlation of 0.899 on the held-out set. Across 684 evaluated images, only eight achieved less than 85% prediction accuracy. Degradation studies—introducing controlled perturbations such as Gaussian noise, blur, and illumination shifts—confirmed that predicted quality scores decreased consistently as visual distortions intensified. Complementing quantitative analysis, four Class Activation Mapping (CAM) methods (Grad-CAM, HiResCAM, EigenCAM, Grad-CAM++) were used to analyze model attention. These visualizations such as in Figure 7, revealed that, in several failure cases, attention drifted toward background regions instead of the subject’s face, suggesting shortcut learning correlated to dataset biases in lighting and background distribution. Importantly, since the IQA focuses only on perceptual metrics, these limitations reflect dataset characteristics, rather than deficiencies in the IQA design, and the results remain valid for assessing the low-level quality of ontology-conditioned synthetic outputs.

E. VISUAL ATTRIBUTE EXTRACTION VALIDATION

To verify the correlation between the generated images and the ontology-based labels, we executed the visual attribute validation stack for a total of 750 samples, that compare the ontology generated descriptions with the physical measurements and high-level semantic attributes with the driver depictions, from the model described in subsection III-D. First, the quantitative analysis between the attribute-based matching and LLM-based semantic comparison, reveals a clear shift in how similarity is evaluated. As shown in Table 4, the mean similarity score improves from 44.42% to 60.51% with the standard deviation remaining nearly unchanged ($\pm 15\%$), indicating a preservation of variability across samples, instead of simply inflating the similarity score. More importantly, the distribution of similarity scores changes notably. The semantic comparison redistributes the majority of samples (71.02%) into the 0.6-0.8 range,

(a) CAM visualization on a low-accuracy prediction. The model focuses on background areas instead of the face.

(b) CAM visualization on a high-accuracy prediction. The model correctly attends to facial regions.

FIGURE 7. Examples of CAM-based explainability for image quality predictions. These visualizations help us understand the model’s decision-making process and highlight cases of shortcut learning.

whereas for attribute matching concentrates a large portion of samples in the lower ranges (0.2-0.6). At the same time, the

TABLE 4. Comparison of LLM-based validation results two strategies.

Similarity Score	Attribute-Matching	Semantic Comparison
Mean Average (%)	44.42	60.51
Standard Deviation (%)	15.12	15.44
Distribution of Similarity Scores		
Values 0.8 – 1.0 (%)	0.00	0.41
Values 0.6 – 0.8 (%)	2.44	71.02
Values 0.4 – 0.6 (%)	41.22	6.53
Values 0.2 – 0.4 (%)	44.08	20.40
Values 0.0 – 0.2 (%)	12.24	1.63

FIGURE 8. Visual reinforcement of the LLM achieved distribution for similarity scores.

proportion of very low similarity scores (0.0-0.2) drops from 12.24% to 1.63%. This shift suggests that the LLM captures contextual relationships between attributes and recognizes partial semantic agreement, that is not reflected in strict attribute-level comparisons.

The histogram in Figure 8, further reinforces this observation by illustrating the structural difference between the two evaluation strategies. The attribute matching distribution is spread across lower similarity ranges, reflecting its sensitivity to exact mismatches across all attributes. In contrast, the semantic comparison distribution is more concentrated around higher similarity scores, which reveals that the LLM can evaluate overall consistency, rather than penalizing each mismatch equally. Consequently, the distribution is not collapsed into uniformly high values, and instead forms a distinct peak, showcasing the LLM maintains its discriminative capability while shifting the interpretation of similarity. This confirms that the semantic comparison introduces a different evaluation perspective, rather than acting as a simple rescaling of attribute-based scores.

Qualitative analysis of selected samples shown in Table 5, further demonstrates the role of the LLM as a context-aware evaluator. In cases with higher similarity scores, the LLM identifies strong agreement in key behavioral attributes (e.g. eye, mouth state), even when minor differences exist in secondary attributes, such as demographic. For medium similarity cases, the model provides explanations that reflect partial consistency, highlighting which attributes align and which introduce discrepancies. In low similarity cases, the LLM correctly identifies contradictions between the ontology-defined driver state and the visually extracted attributes. These examples showcase that the LLM does

not perform simple matching, but instead reasons over the relationships between attributes, supporting the claim that the proposed validation stack functions as a semantic consistency evaluation framework, rather than a purely synthetic comparison mechanism.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presented a time-aware, ontology-driven framework for in-cabin driver state assessment, that explicitly bridges symbolic reasoning and perceptual representation. The system unifies multimodal physiological, behavioral and cognitive indicators under a single, semantically grounded model. We proposed a combination of a 4D-DL architecture, with a hybrid reasoning strategy, where we leveraged GCIs for scalable classification, through carefully set thresholds and SWRL rules for contextual and numerical reasoning. This ensures a transparent, explainable and temporally consistent driver-state inference. Unlike, pure data-driven approaches, the framework explicitly encodes domain knowledge, physiological constraints, and causal dependencies, allowing inferred states to be inspected, verified and systematically extended.

To address the interpretability limitations of purely symbolic outputs, we introduced a cross-modal pipeline, that propagates these inferred states into a perceptual domain, through diffusion-based image synthesis. This process is not intended for real-time deployment or safety-critical feedback. Instead, it is a mechanism for qualitative inspection, debugging and validation of reasoning outcomes.

The proposed multi-layer validation stack, showcases how consistency between symbolic inference and visual representation can be assessed, through attribute extraction and LLM-based semantic comparison. This enables a novel form of cross-modal verification. Experimental results confirm that the ontology maintains logical consistency, stable inferential behavior and coherent propagation of semantic states across modalities.

We created a competency questionnaire, which confirmed high conceptual integrity, exclusive and exhaustive physiological classification and consistent propagation of high-level cognitive states across all evaluated routes. Additionally, we use consistency checks that focus on structural and temporal components, demonstrating strict adherence to cardinality, identity and temporal alignment constraints. Nonetheless, inference completeness analysis, exposed localized gaps under rare physiological cases, however these were shown to be systematic and interpretable, outlining clear pathways for targeted rule-base expansion rather than fundamental modeling flaws.

Importantly, the evaluation is positioned as reasoning-centric rather than clinically definitive. The system does not claim external medical validity, but instead establishes a robust foundation for semantically grounded driver state modeling and analysis.

Future work will focus on incorporating real-world datasets, improving semantic alignment evaluation and

TABLE 5. Qualitative examples of semantic comparison.

Case	Ontology Labels	Visual Labels	Similarity
Low (0.3) - 649	eye: closed, fatigue: drowsy	eye: open, fatigue: alert	Score: 0.31
LLM Output: The generated labels exhibit limited semantic consistency with the reference labels. While the 'age' attribute matches exactly, the 'gender' attribute is a significant mismatch (male vs. female), which carries high importance. 'Demographic' also differs ('German' vs. 'White'). The eye and mouth states are inverted (open vs. closed), which directly impacts behavioral interpretation and carries high importance. Accessories are also missing in the generated label. Behaviorally, the inverted eye and mouth states introduce inconsistencies. The reference labels suggest an 'inattentive' and 'atrisk' state, potentially linked to open eyes/mouth and fatigue. The generated labels with 'closed' eyes and mouth might indicate drowsiness or reduced awareness. The 'prompt details' section in the generated label is irrelevant for semantic consistency assessment but highlights the lack of specific prompting information used to generate the image. The overall low similarity score reflects the critical gender mismatch and the inverted eye/mouth states, which are key behavioral indicators.			
Medium (0.5) - 643	eye: closed, mouth: open	eye: closed, mouth: closed	Score: 0.52
LLM Output: The generated labels demonstrate partial semantic consistency with the reference labels. Several attributes show exact matches (age, eye state, mouth state). However, significant inconsistencies exist regarding gender (female vs. male) and demographic (Austrian vs. Black). The accessories attribute is also inconsistent. Behavioral Consistency: The closed eyes and mouth are consistent with potential fatigue or drowsiness, aligning with the 'sleep' fatigue state in the reference label. However, the inconsistent gender and demographic impact the overall behavioral interpretation. This is a major area of inconsistency. The demographic shift from 'Austrian' to 'Black' is a significant departure and raises questions about the underlying generation process. The change in gender also affects this, as it impacts potential cultural context. Unverifiable Attributes: 'attention', 'unresponsiveness', 'prompt details' attributes in the reference and generated labels are not present in the other label set, and therefore cannot be evaluated. The similarity score reflects this, with a moderate score due to the partial matches but with a penalty for the critical gender discrepancy..			
High (0.7) - 612	eye: closed, fatigue: drowsy	eye: closed, fatigue: tired	Score: 0.71
LLM Output: The generated labels show a reasonable degree of semantic consistency with the reference labels. Here's a breakdown. Schema Coverage: The generated labels cover a good portion of the ontology attributes, though some (e.g., 'fatigue', 'attention', 'unresponsiveness', 'accessories') are missing. The 'age' and 'gender' have exact matches. 'eye state' also matches exactly. However, 'mouth state' has a mismatch: the reference label indicates 'open', while the generated label indicates 'closed'. This is a significant discrepancy. Semantic Consistency Rate: The 'middle-aged' age group aligns well. The 'male' gender is consistent. The 'open' eye state is consistent. The discrepancy with the mouth state ('open' vs. 'closed') introduces a potential behavioral inconsistency. Unverifiable Attributes: 'demographic' is different ('American' vs. 'White'). While demographic information is useful, it's less critical for behavioral consistency. 'accessories' is missing in the generated label. 'fatigue', 'attention', and 'unresponsiveness' are also missing and would require further context to assess. If the intent is to depict a person who is 'drowsinesssuspected' (as indicated in the reference label), a closed mouth is less consistent with that state than an open mouth. Given the prioritization of attributes, the mouth state discrepancy is the most important factor impacting the similarity score. The other matches contribute positively, but the mismatch lowers the overall score.			

exploring lightweight or incremental reasoning approaches to move towards real-time applicability. We also aspire in combining each component into an end-to-end pipeline and validate the entire component chain holistically.

Overall this work contributes a step toward interpretable and explainable multimodal AI systems, in which symbolic reasoning and perception are not separate components but as interconnected layers, within a unified analytical framework.

A. REASONER OPTIMIZATION AND DISCUSSION

When deploying an ontology structure there are two points of congestion hindering performance. The complexity of the ontology, which is directly connected to expressivity and the sizes of TBox and ABox, and the performance of the reasoner, whose task is to reach logical conclusions. The optimization of the reasoning process shows that performance is not explicitly dependent on hardware components, and is fundamentally governed by the interaction between ontology expressivity, reasoning strategy and rule structure.

1) REDUCING REASONING COMPLEXITY

In the baseline ontology configuration, we utilized the GCI-style axioms that force a global reasoning over the class hierarchy. Written as class inclusions, these operate at the TBox level, changing the structure of the class hierarchy. When a reasoner, such as Pellet, processes GCIs it is forced to recompute the entire class subsumption hierarchy, considers

all possible combinations of classes and applies tableau expansion rules, during classification, potentially revisiting large parts of the ontology. Therefore, GCIs are evaluated at the ontology level, not just at the instance level. This becomes expensive, when dealing with multiple conditions, such as the physiological measurements, meaning the cross product of those conditions explodes rapidly. Conceptually, this can be translated as $AllClasses \times AllIntersections \times AllRestrictions$, which Pellet must reason over.

The alternative is representing all of the combinations with SWRL rules. Instead of modifying the ontology hierarchy, the reasoner performs rule firing over individual instances. Specifically, it finds the individuals matching the rule body atoms, to then bind the variables and assert the rule head. Note that the SWRLs belong in the instance data -ABox- reasoning scope. Thus, when the ontology is mainly deployed as a data inference engine, SWRLs often outperform GCIs, due to data-driven reasoning, rather than schema-driven. In this case, Pellet instead performs a more straightforward iteration for all ActorStates, checking all rule conditions.

The results shown in the Section V sub-section C include 99 GCI-based axioms that are globally contributing to the reasoning synchronization, combined with 39 SWRL categorization rules. For a total of 138 logical axioms the inference for a batch of 16 samples was calculated to around 90-100 seconds for the inference. When using explicitly SWRL rules, higher constructs that would be previously used

for further classification of physiological measurements, are a direct result for existing rules. This was previously an intermediary step, to enable the GCI axioms. Thus, for the same comparisons as the previous examples, the total number of SWRL rules is set to 119. The Java heap memory, which allows the reasoner to expand its knowledge to perform with higher processing speed, is set to 14GB. The experiments were all executed on a Windows 11 system with 32GB of RAM and an Intel(R) core i7-13650HX CPU.

2) SCALABILITY AND REPRODUCIBILITY

In previous sections, scalability was only slightly referred to and there exist limitations to what the ontology can achieve, given specific hardware constraints. Provided more heap space, the performance of the JVM reasoner will keep improving, as long as the search tree does not explode, given larger batch size and more rules. The baseline 138 logical reasoning statements suffice for the majority of use cases. However, we can increase the reasoning capacity of the ontology and the reasoner, to accommodate for all reasoning combinations, for the physiological measurements. We consider a two-stage ontology execution strategy, that explicitly separates ontology bootstrapping from runtime inference. When calling the reasoner, it is necessary to parse the context of the world, which the ontology residents in. In the first stage, a dedicated bootstrap world is created in which, the base ontology is loaded and enriched with all necessary structures, including core individuals and higher-level SWRL expansions. To fully materialize the rule logic, ensuring that the reasoner will contemplate the rules during inference, multiple synchronization steps are needed, with the resulting ontology stored as a reusable template, effectively capturing a ‘precompiled’ version of the reasoning schema. Following this method, the system avoids repeatedly executing costly rule construction and initialization processes. This can reduce overhead and improve reproducibility, across different testing configurations.

For the second stage, each experiment or processing task, instantiates a fresh local world and loads the prebuilt ontology template into it. Thus, inference is performed in complete isolation. This design prevents cross-run contamination of individuals and inferred facts, critical for iterating batches of temporal data. Furthermore, within each local world, batch-level isolation is maintained through controlled cleanup of outdated assertions, rather than recreating worlds for every batch. Then, the last step is explicit world closure, to ensure that the memory usage remains bounded, showcasing that with this approach larger-scale and iterative reasoning tasks can be executed.

With this approach, we managed to execute the ontology for all 768 possible combination of the physiological measurements, but for the small batch size of 1. For larger batch sizes, this would not execute due to insufficient heap space for the reasoner, showing a clear constraint for our framework, as well as hardware limitations, which must be

taken into consideration. The results for this experimentation are shown in the next sub-section.

3) OPTIMIZATION PERFORMANCE RESULTS

The immediate comparison for the previous optimization efforts are shown in the extended Table 2 in Table 6. This analysis, highlights three distinct system behaviors: the baseline (GCI-based) configuration, the optimized (world-isolated, rule-structured) and the fully SWRL-driven configuration with all 768 rules.

First comparing the baseline to the optimized setup under identical parameters (JVM 14 GB, batch size 16), the optimization yields a noticeable improvement in reasoning efficiency. The reasoning time is reduced from 92.13 seconds to 49.12 seconds ($\approx 47\%$ reduction), while throughput increases from 0.17 to 0.29 states/s ($\approx 70\%$ improvement). This confirms that separating bootstrapping and inference, along with removing GCIs, in favored of structured rule execution, significantly improves runtime performance. However, this gain is traded-off by a notable increase in CPU utilization, from 123.10% to 570.79%. This indicates that the optimized approach shifts the reasoning process toward a more compute-intensive, concurrent workload. Similarly, memory usage also increases after synchronization (from 20.1% to 36.6%), but remains within acceptable limits, given the available heap space.

However, to fully explore the limits of the reasoning framework, we deliberately evaluated a full rule-driven configuration, where all 768 SWRL rules are activated. This setup was not intended as an optimized deployment strategy but rather as a stress-test to assess the system’s ability, to capture the complete combinatorial space of physiological conditions, which would include all edge cases, some of which already addressed in the CQ analysis. Even though the preparation phase remains fast at 2.32 seconds and comparable to the optimized setup, inference stage becomes significantly more expensive, with reasoning time increasing to 304.10 seconds, more than 6x slower than the optimized configuration. Degradation is also apparent in the reasoner throughput, which drops sharply to 0.05 states/s, indicating hindered scalability, when all rules are actively evaluated. Additionally, memory utilization rises to 64.9%, suggesting the reasoner struggles to handle the expanded rule set efficiently. Since CPU utilization persists, similar to the optimized case, the system becomes computationally saturated, without efficient pruning or structuring of rule execution.

Despite this performance degradation, utilizing all the available SWRLs provides a complete semantic coverage. The ontology is able to resolve edge cases that were previously unanswered and identified as gaps through the competency evaluation, eliminating ambiguous high-level states. This confirms that the rule set is sufficiently expressive to capture the full domain space, even though completeness comes at a substantial computational cost. Quantitative analysis shows that out of 7621 labels tested

TABLE 6. Performance results, captured before and after inference including the optimization step.

	Preparation	After Sync	Optim - Prep	Optim - After Sync	All SWRLs -Prep	All SWRLs - After Sync
CPU Util(%)	5.30	123.10	49.7	570.79	76.00	526.3
Memory Util(%)	16.6	20.1	0.8	36.6	0.8	64.9
Reasoning Time (sec)	10.06	92.13	2.31	49.12	2.32	304.102
Throughput (states/s)	-	0.17	-	0.29	-	0.05

FIGURE 9. Three-layer validation pipeline, where each layer represents a different reasoning abstraction.

there were no labels with undefined fatigue, attention and unresponsiveness, with a 37.98% having only undefined attention states, set by design in a few edge cases.

These results highlight a fundamental trade-off in ontology-based reasoning systems. GCI-based reasoning can ensure strong formal semantics, but suffers from global computational overhead. On the other hand, structured SWRL reasoning enables efficient data-driven inference. Nevertheless, excessive reliance on SWRL rules, without structural constraints, will lead to performance degradation, due to combinatorial rule firing. Therefore, the optimal configuration lies in a controlled hybrid approach, where rule expressivity is carefully balanced against computational feasibility.

**APPENDIX
VISUAL-ATTRIBUTE EXTRACTION - PROMPT
ENGINEERING**

The validation pipeline operates as follows: (1) ontology-generated labels are produced from physiological inputs, (2) synthetic images are generated independently, (3) visual attributes are extracted from the images using perception models, (4) both label sets are converted into a unified JSON structure, and (5) an LLM performs attribute-level and semantic-level comparison to assess consistency. This is demonstrated in the flow diagram of Figure 9. The multi-layer validation stack is demonstrated in the following flow diagram.

The physiological and contextual data are processed through the driver-state ontology, to apply the reasoning

rules to infer higher-level states. The ontology produces an enriched label set, that reflects the semantic interpretation of the driver’s condition. The generated images are then analyzed by the perception pipeline. Two components operate in parallel:

- DeepFace, estimating attributes such as age, gender, demographic group,
- Eye-Mouth State Extractor, determining eye and mouth states through facial landmarks and geometric metrics.

The outputs of these models are combined into a structured JSON file containing the visual attributes, detected directly from the generated image. At this stage, the system holds two representations of the same driver. Both label sets are forwarded to the LLM comparison module. This final stage, for semantic consistency evaluation, leverages LangChain and Ollama. Using a custom LLM-handler class, we can abstract the interaction with the local model and expose a simple *ask()* method, that sends a prompt and returns the generated textual response. This design makes the comparison modular and reusable, since the rest of this validation stage does not need to manage model loading or inference details directly.

The LLM becomes useful, when we provide it with information richer than raw equality. In the original prompt, the inputs were the two label sets, a short description of the role that the LLM must support and the output format. Such a simplistic description of the task, enforced the attribute-matching to the LLM. A logical extension is to persuade the model, to understand that some attributes affect more, the behavioral consistency. We tried to guide the model to always consider:

- Schema coverage - the ontology attributes matching the compared label set.
- Exact match rates - the exact match between label attributes.
- Semantic consistency rate - logically consistent attributes if not textually identical
- Unverifiable attributes - presence of ontology attributes that cannot be verified through visual attributes extraction.

Clarifying that the format may not be identical, is also significant for the model, to not keep searching for exact attributes and finally, we found that the model behaved more appropriately, when we provided a prioritization and hierarchy of the attributes from the labels. This way, we can use the LLM for evaluating semantic consistency, such as closed eyes and open mouth may be connected to fatigue. The finalized format for the prompt is provided below:

```

1 prompt = f"""
2 You are an AI that compares two humans based
  on ontology labels.
3 Your task is to check for semantic
  consistency between attributes provided
  in the two labels.
4 Reference human labels: {real_labels}
5 Generated human labels: {generated_labels}
6
7 Compare the labels and output a JSON with:
8 {{
9 "label_matches": {{}},
10 "similarity_score": 0-1,
11 "comment": "Explain semantic consistency
  between the two. "
12 }}.
13 When comparing the labels you can use these
  guidelines:
14 1) Schema coverage: How many ontology
  attributes have a possible match in the
  compared label set.
15 2) Exact match rate: How many aligned label
  attributes, match exactly.
16 3) Semantic consistency rate: How many label
  attributes are logically consistent even
  if not textually identical.
17 4) Unverifiable attributes: ontology
  attributes that cannot be checked
  visually (the attributes non matching to
  other labels).
18
19 Some attributes are more important for
  behavioral consistency.
20
21 Important behavioral indicators:
22 -closed eyes may indicate fatigue or
  drowsiness
23 -open mouth may indicate yawning
24 -emotion may support or contradict fatigue
  state
25
26 Evaluate:
27 1.Attribute-level matches
28 2.Behavioral consistency
29 3.Demographic consistency
30
31 You will be given label formats that don't
  exactly match. for instance the following
  format:
32 - eye_inst (open/closed)
33 - mouth_inst (open/closed)
34 - age group
35 - gender
36 - demographic
37 - emotion
38
39 You have to remember that in this case you
  are evaluating whether the reference
  label is consistent with the generated.
40 Always refer to the following prioritization
  :
41 Important attributes (high weight):
42 -eye_inst
43 -mouth_inst
44 -gender
45
46 Medium importance:
47 -age group
48 -emotion

```

LISTING 2 Semantic comparison prompt.

```

49
50 Low importance:
51 -demographic
52 -accessories
53
54 """
55 return self.llm.ask(prompt)

```

LISTING 2 (Continued.) Semantic comparison prompt.

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